

Industrial Asset Management and Secure Sharing for an XAI Manufacturing Platform

Sangeetha Reji
Digital Public Services
Fraunhofer FOKUS
Berlin, Germany
sangeetha.reji@fokus.fraunhofer.de

Jonas Hetterich
Digital Public Services
Fraunhofer FOKUS
Berlin, Germany
jonas.hetterich@fokus.fraunhofer.de

Stamatis Pitsios
Data Science and Analytics
UBITECH
Athens, Greece
spitsios@ubitech.eu

Vasilis Gkolemi
ATHENA Research and Innovation Center
Athens, Greece
vgkolemis@athenarc.gr

Sergi Perez-Castanos
Tyris AI
Universitat de València
Valencia, Spain
sergi.perez@tyris.ai, pecaser@alumni.uv.es

Minas Pertselakis
Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions
Limassol, Cyprus
minas@suite5.eu

Abstract—Explainable AI (XAI) is an emerging field that aims to address how black-box decisions of AI systems are made, by attempting to understand the steps and models involved in this decision-making. XAI in manufacturing is supposed to deliver predictability, agility, and resiliency across targeted manufacturing apps. In this context, large amounts of data, which can be of high sensitivity and various formats need to be securely and efficiently handled. This paper proposes an Asset Management and Secure Sharing solution tailored to the XAI and Manufacturing context in order to tackle this challenge. The proposed asset management architecture enables an extensive data management and secure sharing solution for industrial data assets. Industrial data can be pulled, imported, managed, shared, and tracked with a high level of security using this design. This paper describes the solution’s overall architectural design and gives an overview of the functionalities and incorporated technologies of the involved components, which are responsible for data collection, management, provenance, and sharing as well as for overall security.

Index Terms—Explainable Artificial Intelligence(XAI), REST API, Data Provenance, Access Policies, Intellectual property rights (IPRs)

I. INTRODUCTION

Vast amounts of data enable the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems by automatic recognition of patterns within them [1]. Over the past few years, Industry 4.0 (known as the “Fourth Industrial Revolution”, “smart manufacturing”, or “industrial internet”) has built an intelligent network of devices, machines, and systems for manufacturing industries with the help of communication and technology. With the advancement of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) algorithms, AI systems are using them to be a part of Industry 4.0 [2]. Even though the benefits of AI for the manufacturing industry are indisputable, the users of such solutions have little knowledge about how AI makes decisions. This is called the “black box” effect and as a result of this, large industrial operations do not put much trust in AI solutions.

Considering the impact of the predictions made by AI systems on the decision-making processes of industrial operations, it is crucial to develop mechanisms to provide insights to users on AI predictions. The development of these mechanisms and the insights that are presented to the users have given birth to a research field of its own, known as Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) [1]. XAI solutions make the AI system comprehensible in every step and actionable at multiple layers.

Large manufacturing industries leverage the amounts of data they produce to build smart XAI models that can help them in quality inspection, production monitoring, measurement planning, etc. An integral part of building such an XAI solution is the efficient and effective handling of industrial data. This paper introduces the methodology and architecture for efficient industrial asset handling and secure sharing solutions in the context of building an XAI platform. In this context, an industrial asset includes the data created in industrial surroundings to the explanations and predictions made by the XAI models.

The methodology and architecture defined in this paper facilitate the processes of industrial data being imported, stored, transformed, managed, shared, and also tracked with a high level of security. For this particular use case, the methodology comprises five core topics, which are Industrial Data Ingestion, Security and Privacy, Trust Considerations, Industrial Assets Sharing, and Industrial Assets Provenance and IPR Handling. The architecture is built around components that facilitate each of these topics.

For each of these topics, the state-of-the-art analysis is presented in Section II. Followed by that, Section III comprises a detailed description of them and Section IV includes the architectural design and a description of each of the components that is developed to enable these topics. Section V is the description of real-life use cases of the proposed asset management and secure sharing landscape, and Section VI

concludes this paper.

II. EXISTING THEORIES & PREVIOUS WORK

This section presents the state-of-the-art analysis of the methodology and technologies used to build the industrial asset management and secure sharing solution presented in this paper.

Industrial data ingestion describes the process of transporting data from external sources to a target system in the most performant way possible. A well-known data ingestion and transformation technique available today is the ETL principle [3]. It stands for Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) processes and as the name stands, this principle covers the whole data lifecycle from extraction, transformation, and storing in a database. Even though the ETL principle performs basic data transformations such as cleansing, aggregation, joining, and splitting, it is not efficient enough to work with a large volume of heterogeneous data.

With the rise of technology platforms, the evolution of cloud and computing technologies has resulted in the design and implementation of protocols that are directed toward the security of the data in motion and data access control. Some of the examples are GridFTP [4], GridCopy [5], and IPsec [6]. Accompanying these protocols are some of the widely used Access Control Mechanisms (ACM) that eliminate any unauthorized data access or data misuse. Examples include Discretionary Access Control (DAC), Role Based Access Control (RBAC), and Identity Based Access Control (IBAC) [7] [8]. Along with these security mechanisms, data anonymization is the task where the information that may include personal and sensitive data in any collected dataset is transformed in a way that the privacy of the individuals is preserved while reducing the privacy risks and maintaining the data utility [9].

Along with the necessity of security mechanisms in data in motion and data access control, the need for efficient identity and authorization management in cloud solutions is indisputable. Some of the dominant identity management models are the Isolated (or Silo) Model [10], Central Model [11], and Federated Model [11]. For the realization of identity management, some of the technologies available are, OpenID Connect ¹, OAuth 2.0 ², and SAML 2.0.

Data marketplaces are a new business model where data from various sources are collected, aggregated, processed, enriched, bought, and sold. In this direction, the GAIA-X ³ initiative aims to develop the foundations and set the standards of a federated, open data infrastructure that strengthens the ability to both access and share data securely and confidently [12]. The IDS (Industrial Data Spaces) ⁴ was proposed in 2019 by the IDS Association to enable a “network of trusted data” built on the core principles of sovereignty, protection of confidence, decentralization, and security [13].

Another important concept of Industry 4.0, which aims to establish production chains and manufacturing processes increasingly without human involvement is data provenance. It contains metadata that describes the actual industrial data. The World Wide Web Consortium(W3C) has developed the W3C PROV standard that consists of a data model (PROV-DM) ⁵ that defines a common vocabulary for data provenance [14]. It is common knowledge that the combination of multiple datasets usually leads to the generation of new valuable information and knowledge which can increase the performance levels of AI models. Intellectual property rights (IPRs) [15] are defined in these cases in order to safeguard the rights of the data owners over their content. With respect to the standard open data licenses, the most commonly used ones are Public Domain, Creative Commons ⁶, Open Data Commons ⁷, and Community Data License Agreement (CDLA)⁸.

The proposed methodology and architecture in this paper combine all these core topics to build a landscape for industrial asset management and secure sharing. It combines the technology to ingest data periodically from large industrial operations and defines a fixed data model into which all data is transformed. This results in efficient handling of the growing volume of heterogeneous data. Different versions of the datasets are stored along with the metadata which helps in keeping track of evolving datasets over a longer period of time. For the secure handling of data, access control mechanisms are put in place and there is also an AI marketplace where all assets including the datasets to AI models and scripts created in XAI pipelines can be traded. The methodology along with the key considerations and challenges of industrial asset management and secure sharing is described in detail in the following section.

III. METHODOLOGY

As mentioned earlier, five core topics were identified to build the industrial asset management and secure sharing architecture, which are, Industrial Data Ingestion, Security and Privacy, Trust Considerations, Industrial Assets Sharing, and finally, IPR Handling and Industrial Assets Provenance. This section further explains the importance of these topics along with key challenges and considerations to build components that facilitate them.

A. Industrial Data Ingestion

Industrial Data Ingestion is a critical technology for any industrial data management system because it helps the users to make sense of the complex and growing volume of data that is produced periodically. Data ingestion techniques can be classified as streamed, batch processing, or a combination of both known as lambda architecture. Streaming data is the collection and transfer of data in real-time while batch processing collects the data in batches over scheduled intervals. Lambda

¹<https://openid.net/connect/>

²<https://oauth.net/2/>

³<https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

⁴<https://www.internationaldataspaces.org/>

⁵<https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

⁶<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/?lang=en>

⁷<https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/>

⁸<https://cdla.dev/>

architecture consists of both real-time and batch methods. A major challenge for collecting and processing industrial data is that the incoming data should be able to address different requirements. In the case of training data used for XAI pipelines, the data ingestion system must be flexible enough to integrate heterogeneous data. Also, to produce quality explanations along with predictions, it is important that the data is clear and comprehensive. This paper proposes the following components to tackle these industrial data ingestion challenges:

- Registry/Metadata manager stores the metadata of assets stored in the database. It stores and maintains the meta-data information that is used to extensively describe every AI artifact (i.e., dataset, AI model, pipeline, or result).
- File Data Harvester converts all heterogeneous data into a common concrete data model. It transforms data from file(s) to a structured form according to a data model and stores it in the database.
- API Data Harvester is used to harvest data from data-providing APIs and transform it into a common data model and ingest it into the database.
- File/Data Manager provides an interface to present available binary file assets to a user and can also be used to ingest data that is in binary format.

B. Security and Privacy

The research areas of security and privacy in the scope of this paper are the security of the data in motion and the data access control. For the secure transportation of data from one place to another, large efforts have been performed toward the design and implementation of protocols that can efficiently perform this operation with high throughput, fairness, and stability in various layers of the TCP/IP model. Besides this secure transfer of data from one point to another, for the assurance of data confidentiality and data integrity, it is important to guarantee the selective restriction of access to any critical or valuable resources. Access Control Mechanisms (ACMs) cover all the authentication, authorization, access regulation, and access auditing aspects of industrial data. Even though security and privacy technologies are not scarce, for our use case, ACMs must manage dynamic and evolving data access control during the lifetime of the platform. Since the data processed in this platform is for building XAI models, the quality of the data is of utmost importance. The security and privacy methods incorporated in the proposed architecture try to deliver this through the following components:

- Policy Engine regulates the access to the underlying assets of the platform by formulating an access control decision for each access request that is received.
- Policy Editor offers a novel and user-friendly user interface through which the owner of the asset will be able to perform all the access policy lifecycle management operations.

C. Trust Considerations

Identity and Authorization Management incorporates all the processes and policies that are related to the management of digital assets. It includes, the user who utilizes his/her digital identity to perform an action, the Identity Provider (IdP) who is responsible for the generation, update, maintenance, and deletion of the digital identity as well as the execution of the authentication process and finally the Service Provider (SP) who is responsible for providing the underlying service(s) that the user is willing to utilize and is relying on the IdP for the identity verification process. Some of the key challenges identified in the area of identity management and accountability are when applications have a hybrid architecture of having both on-premises and cloud applications. If connectors are utilized in an identity management solution, it has to be kept up to date with the update in applications in a short span of time. Also, accountability management for a cloud application that scales elastically increases the need for efficient logging techniques with the proper scope and scale. In our architecture, the following component is in charge of identifying the needs and delivering efficient identity and authorization management solutions.

- Identity and Authorization Management provides the holistic user account management lifecycle by being the single core identity provider of the platform that performs the registration, verification, and authentication operations of users.

D. Industrial Assets Sharing

In the scope of this paper, industrial assets are considered digital assets related to industry data or derived from it, such as processed data, trained AI models, experimental results, or analytic reports. Even though the digital asset trading industry is thriving, there are several challenges such data marketplaces face on technical, economic, and regulatory aspects. There are several trust-related challenges in maintaining the privacy of data marketplaces such as the fear of unintentionally giving away sensitive data, or a fear of losing negotiation power. Some of the technical barriers are the risk of data breaches and the accessibility and interoperability issues that arise from combining data. Also, the data in an AI marketplace should have a mechanism that ensures that the training data is only used for AI pipelines. Careful consideration must be given to cases where the datasets that trained an AI model cannot be provided externally for privacy or other reasons, as the traceability of models from these sources might become cumbersome. The XAI marketplace proposed in this paper contains the following components that attempt to overcome these challenges:

- Metadata Manager stores and maintains the metadata of assets and it has an interface using which the user is allowed to share the AI assets with other departments within or beyond their organization inside the XAI Marketplace.
- Contract Manager facilitates asset sharing between different organizations, their departments, and their users. It

handles all operations regarding smart contracts, contract terms enforcement, and the interaction between end users concerning agreement signing, negotiations, and asset transfer.

E. Industrial Assets Provenance and IPR Handling

Data provenance records contain metadata information of an asset such as "why", "where", "how", "when" and "by whom" was an asset produced. Along with this, if several versions of an asset are created, the database system should support a version control mechanism to store and maintain these versions. Intellectual property rights (IPRs) are licenses that drive the formulation of the decisions related to data access and data sharing and it is defined in order to safeguard the rights of the data owners over their content. One of the major challenges when it comes to storing and maintaining asset provenance records is the scalability of data versioning. The accesses and changes to an asset must be stored synchronously in a separate metadata catalog and must be made available in all cases. As the analysis of big data usually involves the combination and aggregation of multiple datasets which are licensed with different licenses containing different terms and conditions, the challenge of IPR conflict resolution on the produced outcomes and results arises. In our architecture, the functionality of provenance and IPR handling is performed by the following components:

- Provenance Engine tracks data provenance which constitutes all entities, agents, and activities associated with any data operation. It stores data provenance information like "who" performed "which" CRUD-operation involving "which" version of "which" asset.
- Metadata Manager stores the licensing details, such as license type, IPR owner, and the data assets that are automatically filtered based on the respective access policies and IPRs in its interface.

The following section presents the overall architecture design that facilitates all of the above-mentioned methods for systematic and structured industrial asset management and sharing in the context of building an XAI pipeline. The functionalities of each of the components in the architecture are described in detail along with the technologies used to build them.

IV. ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

On the basis of the topics presented in the previous section, this section describes the complete architectural design of the proposed solution including the functionalities and technology stack of the individual components. Fig. 1 shows the architecture image and Fig. 2 shows the data and control flow diagram of all the components.

A. Data Storage Service

1) *Assets Store with Version Control* : The Assets Store with Version Control is the component responsible for storing all industrial assets. The following asset types are stored in this component:

Fig. 1. Industrial Asset Management and Secure Sharing Architecture

- Files of different types, including data files, data analysis or processing script files, and any other binary files. It provides an endpoint for adding, updating, and removing the file(s) and getting the specified version of the file(s).
- Structured Data conforming to a specific data model. It also provides multiple endpoints to perform CRUD operations on this data.

The Assets Store is developed with PostgreSQL⁹, which is a powerful and efficient relational database management solution. Structured data, which comes along with a data model, can be efficiently stored and managed in a relational database such as PostgreSQL¹⁰. Binary and non-binary files are stored in two separate databases. Every asset has a UUID attached to it and all assets can be queried from the Assets Store using its UUID. The version control feature of the Assets Store allows the storage of different versions of an asset. CRUD operations on different versions of an asset are also available through a Flask API¹⁰.

B. Data Handler

The Data Handler is composed of four components.

1) *File/Data Manager*: The File/Data Manager (FDM) offers a comprehensive view of the assets belonging to a user. By using the FDM, the user can carry out all CRUD (create, read, update, delete) operations on the assets that are accessible to them.

2) *Data Exporter*: Data-exporter simplifies the process of exporting datasets for users, allowing them to easily export any dataset to their local machine with just a few clicks. It offers the capabilities of listing all the available datasets for the user, setting the format of the exported document (csv or xlsx), slicing rows and/or columns before exporting, and a user-friendly frontend to make the process of exporting data easier. Additionally, the component has an API that allows other components to integrate and access all the capabilities of the frontend. The Data-exporter component is built using JavaScript frameworks, with Nuxt¹¹ used for the frontend and Nest¹² for the backend.

⁹<https://www.postgresql.org/>

¹⁰<https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/2.2.x/>

¹¹<https://nuxtjs.org/>

¹²<https://nestjs.com/>

3) *API Data Harvester*: The API Data Harvester (ADH) constitutes a solution for an automated data ingestion procedure offering a pipeline management system, which allows for an individualized and schedulable transformation and transport of large amounts of data from external APIs into the Assets Store. As can be seen in Fig. 2 it therefore represents a bridge connecting external data sources to the Assets Store while ensuring that the data format aligns with the requirements. It consists of four individual components, namely *Scheduler*, *Importer*, *Transformer* and *Exporter*, all of which are implemented in either Java or Kotlin using the Vertx-Framework¹³, which enables an efficient handling of multiple tasks in an asynchronous and concurrent manner. The backend is tied together behind the hood of a frontend, implemented in Vue.js¹⁴ which allows the user to manage his data pipelines in an efficient manner via an interactive graphical user interface.

4) *File Data Harvester* : The File Data Harvester (FDH) represents the solution for the alternative way through which data can be ingested into the Assets Store. Instead of harvesting external APIs as done by the ADH, data can also be extracted from files, which are already present in the Assets Store. It thus constitutes an internal conversion module, allowing for the extraction of data out of binary sources and the storing of this data in structured format as required by ensuingly operating processes. Similar to the ADH, the FDH offers a GUI through which the user, after authenticating himself, can select the file he wants to harvest the data from before being guided through the data transformation process. After adding metadata properties to the extracted data it can then be saved as structured data in the Assets Store, making it available for further platform-internal operations. The backend of the FDH is written in Python and offers its functionalities as web services via an API implemented in Flask¹¹. The frontend consuming these services is a JavaScript application realized in the Vue.js¹⁵ framework.

C. XAI Marketplace

The XAI Marketplace is responsible for providing a user with the means to view, search and discover data assets of interest and for facilitating the process that involves the acquisition of one or more data assets based on a mutually agreed contract between the asset provider and the asset consumer. It consists of 2 components: the Registry/Metadata Manager and the Contract Manager.

1) *Registry/Metadata Manager* : The Registry/Metadata Manager handles, stores and maintains the metadata information that is used to extensively describe every asset. It provides the appropriate user interface for the asset owners to define/update or generally view the corresponding metadata, and for any user to search for assets of interest or view their metadata in alignment with each asset's policies and IPRs as provided by the Access Manager.

2) *Contract Manager*: The Contract Manager facilitates asset sharing between different organizations, their departments, and their users. When a potential asset "consumer" expresses interest in an asset, the Contract Manager allows the asset owner to draft, edit and manage an agreement in a machine-readable format. Through the user interface, the involved parties can negotiate over the terms and conditions, and monitor the status of the whole process. The Contract Manager is then responsible to enforce the agreed terms (i.e. access to a specific asset with specific rights for a defined period), which are safely stored in the XMANAI distributed ledger in the form of a smart contract.

D. Provenance Engine

The Provenance Engine (PE) documents all CRUD actions being performed on an asset. This documentation process implicitly creates and extends the lineage of each asset, giving an overview of its "lifeline". This allows for a detailed tracking and comprehension of how different asset versions emerged and are related to one another. The metadata is being stored as triplets according to the W3C PROV-O ontology. The PE is a pure backend component offering its functionalities as a web service. It provides services to either document CRUD operations or retrieve the lineage of a specified asset. The first type of services is being utilized by the Assets Store, which is actively involved in every asset manipulation activity and thus can efficiently trigger the respective documentation process via the PE. The second type of services is being used by Marketplace UI in order to give the user an overview of an asset's lineage as well as direct access to its different versions. The PE is implemented in Python, offering its services via a Flask API and storing the metadata in a Virtuoso RDF Triple Store¹⁵.

E. Access Manager

The Data Access Manager is the component responsible for the access control operations that prevents the stored industrial assets from unauthorised or unintentional access. The component is composed of two major modules, namely the Policy Engine that undertakes the access control process as well as the policies enforcement and the Policy Editor that undertakes the complete lifecycle management of the access policies.

1) *Policy Engine*: Policy Engine provides the required robust access control mechanism which is built around a solid authorization engine that performs the enforcement of the access control policies as defined by the owner of the industrial asset. It formulates a dynamic access control model that is based on the provided access policies. The policies are instantly deployed, updated and enforced by the mechanism handling all their evolution. Additionally, it provides the appropriate access control decision that will either grant or deny access to the requestor by evaluating all access requests against this access control model. Finally, it provides a set of

¹³<https://vertx.io/>

¹⁴<https://vuejs.org/>

¹⁵<https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>

well-defined API interfaces for the access control mechanism suitable for the reception and evaluation of all access requests. The module is implemented utilizing the policy enforcement framework Casbin¹⁶ as well as the Java-based library jCasbin¹⁷ along with Java-based framework SpringBoot¹⁸.

2) *Policy Editor*: The Policy Editor performs all the life-cycle management operations for the access policies. In particular, it enables all the CRUD operations of the access policies from the owner of the industrial asset via a user-friendly graphical interface while in parallel undertaking their storage and reuse upon the needs of owner. The module is also implemented using Casbin¹⁷, jCasbin¹⁸ and the Java-based framework SpringBoot¹⁹, as well as PostgreSQL¹⁰ for storage purposes.

F. Identity & Authorisation Management

The Identity & Authorisation Management component is responsible for providing the single core identity provider that is utilised in order to perform the user account management lifecycle. To this end, it facilitates the user registration process implementing the mechanism for the registration and verification of an organisation, as well as the update of the organisation’s profile. It implements also the user’s invitation and registration process as well as all the CRUD operations on the user’s profile. In addition to this, it implements the robust authentication mechanism that verifies and controls the access based on the provided credentials. Finally, it facilitates the authorization operations for the intercommunication between the various components on a technical endpoint level based on the rules defined by the administrator. The component is implemented using the identity and access management framework Keycloak¹⁹, the reactive-stack web framework of Spring WebFlux²⁰, the access-control framework of Spring Security²¹ and PostgreSQL¹⁰ for storage purposes.

V. XMANAI USE CASE

Explainable Manufacturing Artificial Intelligence (XMANAI)²² is a Research & Innovation Action (RIA), aiming at the research, design, deployment, piloting, and market preparation for a novel AI platform for manufacturing. It aims to design, develop and deploy a novel Explainable AI Platform powered by XAI models that inspire trust, augment human cognition and solve concrete manufacturing problems with value-based explanations. XMANAI platform is tested and validated with four demonstrators involving the manufacturing value chain stakeholders, diverse actors’ needs and data sources. The components explained in the previous section play the role of an asset management and secure sharing layer that handles an industrial asset lifecycle from

Fig. 2. Industrial Asset Management and Secure Sharing Data Flow Diagram

ingestion to transformation and makes it ready for utilization in the XAI pipelines. This section describes the four real-life manufacturing use cases and the various types of assets that can be handled in the asset management and secure sharing components.

A. Ford - AI for Production Optimization

The production lines of the Ford of Spain engine plant suffer from unplanned and planned stoppages that are affecting their continuous availability. With the help of an XAI platform, Ford will ingest, manage and analyze the data acquired by the corporate systems in order to build XAI models that can create predictions to optimize the line throughput of the current system. The data from FORD systems is stored in an SQL server. To make these data sources accessible to the XMANAI platform, the information in SQL servers is queried and converted to text files and uploaded to the File/Data Manager.

B. Whirlpool - AI for product demand planning

The requirement of Whirlpool is in Demand Planning for the Italian market and XMANAI can provide them with a trusted AI platform that will allow for batch data ingestion on a weekly basis, execution of scheduled, periodic demand forecasting models and understanding of the expected actions for production planning at the factory level. The data sources of Whirlpool are stored in the Google Cloud Platform(GCP) and are available as Google BigQuery tables. These can be ingested into the asset management layer either using the API Data Harvester through the Rest-API Endpoint provided by Google or File/Data Manager after querying the data and transforming them to text files.

C. CNH - AI For Process/Product Quality Optimization

The case of CNH tractor plant in Italy is similar to that of Ford with unplanned stoppages occurring in the assembly line. Using the asset ingestion techniques in the XMANAI platform, CNH will ingest and analyze real-time batch data acquired from the CNHi systems. The data sources of the CNH include

¹⁶<https://casbin.org/>

¹⁷<https://github.com/casbin/jcasbin>

¹⁸<https://spring.io/>

¹⁹<https://www.keycloak.org/>

²⁰<https://docs.spring.io/spring-framework/docs/current/reference/html/web-reactive.html>

²¹<https://docs.spring.io/spring-security/reference/index.html>

²²<https://ai4manufacturing.eu/>

machinery and maintenance data and these are available as files that are extracted and ingested into the asset management layer using the File/Data Manager.

D. Unimetrik - AI For Smart Semi-Autonomous Hybrid Measurement Planning

Unimetrik uses metrological studies to test the tolerances of their machine parts. The XMANAI platform will help Unimetrik to speed up the programming and design of quality control strategies during the strategy phase of the metrological study. The data source of Unimetrik is a Data Lake and can be accessed through REST API calls. For the data ingestion, API Data Harvester can access the REST API endpoints or if available as files, File/Data Manager can be used to upload them.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an overview of an industrial asset management and sharing landscape that facilitates data harvest, ingestion, transformation, trading and tracking with a high level of security in the context of building and training XAI models. The industrial assets referenced in this paper are digital assets in the form of a relational table or binary file which are related to manufacturing data or derived from it, such as processed data, trained XAI models, pipelines, scripts, experimental results, and analytic reports.

Five methods are identified as the important aspects of building a systematic and secure industrial asset management system and the importance of these methods and the key challenges in realizing them are described in detail in this paper. These methods serve as the building blocks of industrial asset management and secure sharing architecture. This architecture contains several components with functionalities to achieve the objectives of the previously mentioned methods and to tackle the key challenges. This paper also presents several real-life use cases for these components which are carried out in context to the XMANAI project.

A. Future Work

The next steps in developing the proposed asset management and secure sharing solution focus on extending the functionalities of each of the components and identifying more methods and technologies that can be used to broaden the use cases of this solution. The Assets Store with Version Control, which is the central database component that supports storing several versions of an asset, has the opportunity to incorporate sophisticated versioning mechanisms similar to Git. It uses PostgreSQL to store assets that have a limit on size of the binary files and alternate solutions can be used to handle big data and large binary files. The data handler components do not support all file types and it can be extended to add support for more file types.

Along with extending the functionalities of the existing components, technologies to add features such as data pre-processing, data visualization or data enrichment can bring

more use cases to the existing architecture. The above-mentioned XMANAI use cases also need to be tested extensively to identify the performance and limitations of the proposed solution.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to this work has been carried out within the context of the XMANAI project. The XMANAI project is being funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Programme (Grant Agreement No 957362).

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Sofianidis, J. M. Rozanec, D. Mladenic, and D. Kyriazis, "A review of explainable artificial intelligence in manufacturing," *CoRR*, vol. abs/2107.02295, 2021.
- [2] I. Ahmed, G. Jeon, and F. Piccialli, "From artificial intelligence to explainable artificial intelligence in industry 4.0: A survey on what, how, and where," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 5031–5042, 2022.
- [3] V. Theodorou, A. Abelló, M. Thiele, and W. Lehner, "Frequent patterns in etl workflows: An empirical approach," *Data & Knowledge Engineering*, vol. 112, pp. 1–16, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169023X16302713>
- [4] G. Alliance, "Gridftp-universal data transfer for the grid," *White Paper. September*, vol. 5, 2000.
- [5] R. Kettimuthu, W. Allcock, L. Liming, J.-P. Navarro, and I. Foster, "Gridcopy: Moving data fast on the grid," in *2007 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium*. IEEE, 2007, pp. 1–6.
- [6] H. Dhall, D. Dhall, S. Batra, and P. Rani, "Implementation of ipsec protocol," in *2012 Second International Conference on Advanced Computing & Communication Technologies*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 176–181.
- [7] R. El Sibai, N. Gemayel, J. Bou Abdo, and J. Demerjian, "A survey on access control mechanisms for cloud computing," *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 31, no. 2, p. e3720, 2020, e3720 ett.3720. [Online]. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/ett.3720>
- [8] K. Punithasurya and S. J. Priya, "Analysis of different access control mechanism in cloud," *International Journal of Applied Information Systems*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 34–39, 2012.
- [9] B. Fung, K. Wang, A. Fu, and P. Yu, *Introduction to Privacy-Preserving Data Publishing: Concepts and Techniques*, ser. Chapman & Hall/CRC Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery Series. CRC Press, 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.de/books?id=fUopcSpQuNMC>
- [10] M. Laurent and S. Bouzeffrane, *Digital identity management*. Elsevier, 2015.
- [11] B. Zwattendorfer, T. Zefferer, and K. Stranacher, "An overview of cloud identity management-models," *WEBIST (1)*, pp. 82–92, 2014.
- [12] "Gaia-x." [Online]. Available: <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIAx/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>
- [13] "International data spaces," <https://www.internationaldataspaces.org/>, accessed: 2023-03-14.
- [14] G. Closa, J. Masó, B. Proß, and X. Pons, "W3c prov to describe provenance at the dataset, feature and attribute levels in a distributed environment," *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, vol. 64, pp. 103–117, 2017.
- [15] G. Yang and K. E. Maskus, "Intellectual property rights and licensing: An econometric investigation," *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, vol. 137, no. 1, pp. 58–79, 2001.